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**PRAGMATIC STRATEGIES IN MARKET NEGOTIATIONS: A STUDY OF
IMPLICATURE AND POLITENESS AMONG TRADERS IN RURAL NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The present research explores the pragmatic strategies used in rural Nigerian markets, (Akparabong and Bendeghe Ekiem markets in Cross River State) focusing on implicature and politeness within buyer-seller negotiations. Using qualitative methods, including participant observation and interviews, the study reveals that traders frequently employ indirect speech and culturally sensitive politeness strategies to manage face, maintain social harmony, and achieve successful transactions. Findings demonstrate the significant role of context, shared knowledge, and cultural norms in shaping market discourse. Findings reveal that meaning in these informal settings depends strongly on mutual cultural understanding and the use of non-verbal signals and situational context rather than literal meanings. The study concludes that pragmatic competence in such settings reflects a dynamic interplay between language use and community values, with relevance to educational practices in language as well as communication across cultures. The study also concludes that effective communication in market discourse depends not only on linguistic competence but also on pragmatic awareness of context, intention, and social relationships.

Keywords: pragmatics, Implicature, Politeness strategies, Market discourse, Rural Nigeria, Speech acts

Introduction

This study investigates how traders and buyers use implicature and politeness during negotiation. Implicature refers to the technical term in the Pragmatics subfield of linguistics coined by Grice (1975), which refers to what is suggested in an utterance even though it is neither expressed nor strictly implied by the utterance. Implicature refers to an indirect meaning of an utterance derived

from its conventional use. This research aims to uncover how meaning is implied rather than stated, and how politeness strategies are employed to maintain face and navigate social relationships.

Language is more than a tool for conveying information; it is a means of performing actions and maintaining relationships. Pragmatics, a linguistic domain, investigates how speakers and listeners interpret language about context, and provides a framework for understanding how speakers navigate meaning beyond literal expression. In culturally rich settings such as local markets, pragmatic strategies are essential for smooth interaction, especially in negotiations where social and economic goals intersect. This view is supported by Blom & Gumperz (1972), foundational for understanding how context drives code-switching very applicable to switching in markets, where different buyers require communicative strategies.

In rural Nigerian markets, bargaining is not only a routine economic activity but also a culturally structured communicative event. Hymes (1974), emphasizes contextual and cultural factors in language use, ideal for studying market rural interactions. Buyers and sellers engage in complex exchanges that involve persuasion, refusal, compromise, and relationship-building. These interactions rely heavily on implicature and politeness strategies that reflect local social norms and values. Despite their importance, such everyday pragmatic phenomena remain under-researched, particularly in non-urban Nigerian contexts.

In marketplaces, communication goes beyond words: it is shaped by gestures, tone, shared background knowledge, and cultural cues. Unlike formal communication, market interactions rely heavily on pragmatic competence—the ability to use and interpret language based on context. In Nigeria’s rural markets, this competence enables buyers and sellers to negotiate, joke, persuade, and build rapport, despite diverse linguistic backgrounds.

Language Practices and Price Negotiation in African Informal Markets

Informal markets across Africa function not only as commercial centers but also as dynamic spaces for social interaction, where language plays a key role in negotiation and identity expression. Researchers have observed that the act of alternating languages in interaction, known as code switching, is frequently employed deliberately to achieve specific purposes by both traders and buyers to influence outcomes and navigate diverse cultural settings.

For example, Erastus (2003) studied the Maasai Market in Nairobi and found that traders commonly switch between Swahili, English, Sheng, and local dialects depending on the interaction. While English may be used to signal formality or appeal to wealthier customers (often leading to higher pricing), Swahili and Sheng are used to establish familiarity or solidarity, which can foster trust and more favorable pricing. These language choices serve as social signals, supporting the idea that language use in such contexts goes beyond communication to shape interpersonal dynamics. This also applies to Akparabong and Bendeghe Ekiem markets in Cross River State. Code-switching use during bargaining in Africa markets signals solidarity among buyers and sellers.

Similarly, Ayoola (2009) highlighted how sellers in Lagos meat markets strategically mix Yoruba, English, and Nigerian Pidgin to facilitate transactions with a linguistically diverse clientele. This flexible language use helps smooth interactions, manage power dynamics, and create rapport—key elements in successful bargaining.

Tanimu and Suleiman (2023), focusing on Masaka Market in Nigeria, also found that Nigerian Pidgin acts as a unifying language among speakers of different ethnic backgrounds. They noted

that traders switch codes not just for clarity, but to build trust and reflect shared cultural understanding, aligning with Bourdieu's (1991) theory of linguistic capital, where language choice can provide economic and symbolic advantage. In Akparabong and Bendeghe Ekiem markets, traders code-switch to the Ndoe and Ejagham languages to indicate companionship. This spirit of goodwill brings about a favourable bargain. Beyond language, bargaining—or haggling—is deeply ingrained in market culture, especially in informal settings. Uzo, Loke, and Nwokporo (2025) reported that a majority of African consumers prefer negotiating prices in open markets rather than accepting fixed prices in supermarkets. This process is more than just economic; it's a form of social interaction that allows buyers and sellers to engage emotionally and culturally, demonstrating how value is shaped not only by supply and demand but also by social connection.

Altogether, these studies suggest that engaging in African market systems effectively requires more than just financial savvy. Traders and buyers must be linguistically adaptable and culturally aware, as language practices and negotiation techniques are deeply interwoven and reflect broader social dynamics such as identity, ethnicity, class, and trust.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to investigate the use of implicature and Politeness among traders in rural Akparabong and Bendeghe Ekiem markets in Nigeria.

The following objectives guide the study:

1. To examine how implicature is used in market negotiations in rural Nigerian contexts.
2. To identify the politeness strategies employed by market participants during price bargaining
3. To explore the cultural influences on pragmatic choices in market interactions.

Research Questions

- 1 Why are implicatures used in the markets as means of negotiation in rural Nigerian contexts?
- 2 How are politeness strategies employed by market participants during price bargaining
- 3 What are the cultural influences on pragmatic choices in market interaction?

Theoretical Framework

This research draws on two core theories in pragmatics:

Grice's Cooperative Principle (1975), particularly the notion of conversational implicature, describes how speakers imply meaning by flouting conversational maxims.

Brown and Levinson's Politeness Theory (1987), which categorizes politeness strategies into positive (solidarity-based) and negative (deference-based) acts to mitigate face-threatening situations.

These theories are used to analyze indirect language use and face-management practices in market interactions.

Methodology

A qualitative, ethnographic approach was adopted. Data were gathered from two major rural markets (Akparabong and Bendeghe Ekiem) in Cross River State, Nigeria through:

Participant Observation: The researcher participated as a customer, observing real-time bargaining conversations.

Semi-structured Interviews: Twenty participants (10 traders and 10 buyers) were interviewed to explain their linguistic choices during negotiation.

The data were recorded, transcribed, and analyzed thematically using pragmatic categories such as implicature, politeness markers, speech acts, and contextual cues.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the market interactions was examined using a pragmatic analytical approach. The focus was on identifying how conversational implicatures and politeness strategies were employed by traders during bargaining exchanges. Each conversation was transcribed and carefully analyzed to identify instances where traders communicated meanings indirectly or relied on shared cultural knowledge to be understood. Particular attention was paid to the use of politeness, such as respectful address forms, indirect offers, and strategies that helped maintain cordial relations during price negotiations. These features were interpreted with reference to Pragmatic theories, while also considering the social setting in which the exchanges took place. The analysis therefore revealed how traders in rural Nigerian markets employ language not only to reach agreements but also to uphold communal values, demonstrate respect for age and status, and preserve harmony in everyday economic interactions.

Findings and Discussion

Use of Implicature

Indirectness was a dominant feature in bargaining. Rather than rejecting an offer outright, sellers often used a metaphor or exaggeration to imply refusal. For example, one trader said:

“Even my grandmother wouldn’t sell it at that price”.

This utterance indirectly communicates that the offer is unacceptably low without using explicit rejection. Such implicatures preserve politeness while still conveying dissatisfaction.

Buyers also used implicature to suggest dissatisfaction or pressure the seller indirectly, for example “Others are selling it cheaper across the road”. Here, the buyer does not directly demand a lower price but implies that better options exist, inviting a counteroffer.

This study highlights the central role of pragmatic competence in everyday communication among traders.

The study affirms that meaning is not inherent in words alone, but emerges from context, shared background knowledge, and interactional cues. In Nigerian rural markets:

Pragmatic meaning is fluid, adaptive, and context-sensitive.

Implicatures allow for economy of expression. Indirectness, politeness, and

Code-switching and informal speech are pragmatic tools that foster in-group identity and ease tension.

Some realistic examples of code-switching between buyers and sellers in a rural market where Ndoe and Ejagham are spoken alongside English or Nigerian pidgin. These examples reflect natural interaction, often switching between local languages and a more dominant or widely understood language for clarity, emphasis, or politeness. For example, Seller in (Ndoe): “Onoh ndem bosehi?” (Do you want to buy fish?) Buyer: “Yes, but how much be this small one?” (switch to pidgin for clarity) Seller: pidgin That one na N400. But if you wan take two, I fit give

am for N500. Code-switching from Ndoe to pidgin helps increase clarity, mainly for discussing prices.

Politeness Strategies

Participants displayed both positive politeness (emphasizing familiarity, solidarity, and group identity) and negative politeness (showing respect and avoiding imposition). Myers-Scotton's (1993) work, focuses on code-switching as a socially motivated choice in African multilingual communities. In the work, he explains language choice about power, identity, and negotiation. The research is significant for analyzing market interactions, where sellers/buyers switch codes for negotiation, politeness, or persuasion. Blommaert (2005), states examples of economic discourse and market negotiation speech, relevant for analyzing power and persuasion in buying and selling. Kuang's (2019) research explores buyer-seller code-switching strategies and how these shape successful transactions. These code-switching strategies enhance effective communication in the markets. Hence, there is the spirit of goodwill between buyers and sellers in rural markets.

Examples of positive politeness include:

“You’re like a sister to me—give me your best price.”

“Because of you, I will take a loss today.”

Another example of politeness/Respect

Seller (Ejagham) “Nkana kit kpa e?” Buyer(pidgin): “Make you give me a better price, abeg. Ino carry enough money”

Negative politeness strategies were more frequent with older traders or unfamiliar customers:

“If you don’t mind, could you add something small?”

“Please, sir, consider this my last price.”

These strategies reflect sensitivity to social hierarchy, relationship-building, and the importance of saving face in communal settings. These strategies reflect Finlayson, Calteaux, & Myers-Scotton’s (1998) work, who demonstrate how speakers switch codes to manage power dynamics, solidarity, and transactional clarity. Their work discusses multilingualism in informal urban and rural settings especially marketplaces.

Cultural Influences on Pragmatic Choices

Cultural norms heavily influenced how language was used in negotiation. Age, gender, and social status shaped how direct or indirect speech acts were. Elders were rarely challenged indirectly. Proverbs and idioms were commonly used to make a point without confrontation. Humor also served as a face-saving device and helped ease tense interactions. Bamgbose, (1991), examines multilingual and language policy in African nations. This study is helpful for framing market language practices in terms of language contact and dominance. Ugot, (2010), research also supports context- specific analysis of identity and pragmatics in communication.

Contextual Meaning is Central to Communication

Words were often ambiguous without physical cues. For example:

“This one wey you carry na fake o!” – The meaning depends on pointing, tone, and facial expression.

“Bring better money, abeg” implies a discount request, not just literal payment. Adegbija, (1994) is essential for interpreting why buyers/sellers may prefer pidgin or English during transactions. Kamwangamalu (2010), work though focuses on education, Kamwangamalu’s study explores code-switching in everyday African discourse, including public and transactional spaces.

Indirect speech and implicature were Frequent:

Rather than saying “This is expensive,” a customer might say *“Ah-ah, this one pass my pocket o!”*—implying it is unaffordable without stating it outright. Essien’s, (1990) study, though, on grammar, is also relevant for market language contact situations in Akparabong and Bendeghe Ekiem where the Ndoe and Ejagham languages are spoken.

Code-Switching and Humor Strengthen Social Bonds

Participants often switched between English, Nigerian Pidgin, Ndoe, Ejagham, or Igbo. Igboanusi’s, (2008) study is relevant to this study because it analyzes conversational strategies involving code-switching in Nigerian English, especially in informal contexts. Ayeomoni, (2006) research on Code-switching and code mixing is similar to this study in that it shows linguistic flexibility and functionality in informal rural economies. Batibo (2005), not only focuses on language shift in Africa, but also highlights code-switching in marketplaces as evidence of language contact and multilingual survival strategies. Nkamigbo’s (2010), study applies to market speech patterns and linguistic negotiation. Nkamigbo focuses specifically on code-switching among bilingual Nigerians, especially in conversation. His work affirms the code-switching

situation in Africa, especially during business transactions. Humor was used to soften negotiation or dismiss insults. The use of implicature and politeness strategies allows interlocutors to navigate price disagreements while preserving social relationships

These strategies are deeply rooted in cultural norms, reflecting how language is shaped by context and community expectations. Okon (2004), helps explain switching to English or Pidgin in market conversations as a means of achieving balance. These findings align with Hymes' theory of communicative competence, which highlights that the appropriateness of speech in context is equally as important as the content of what is spoken.

Conclusion

This study highlights the central role of pragmatic competence in everyday communication among traders and buyers in rural Nigerian markets. The use of implicature and politeness strategies allows interlocutors to navigate price disagreements while preserving social relationships. These strategies are deeply rooted in cultural norms, reflecting how language is shaped by context and community expectations.

Understanding such local pragmatic patterns can contribute to improved language teaching, intercultural communication, and even conflict resolution strategies in multilingual and multicultural societies.

Rural Nigerian markets provide a rich setting for studying real-world pragmatics. Effective communication in these spaces relies not just on shared language, but on shared understanding of context. Market participants use linguistic creativity, non-verbal cues, and cultural knowledge to negotiate meaning, maintain relationships, and achieve their goals. Here, the buyer does not

directly demand a lower price but implies that better options exist, inviting a counteroffer. Al-khatib's (2003) work provides insight into code-switching in commercial and public domains, including shopping contexts. The work supports the social function of language alternation in market-like paces. This study has examined code-switching practices in rural market settings within the Ndoe and Ejagham –speaking communities from a pragmatic perspective. The findings indicate that code-switching is a strategic communicative act, guided by the need to manoeuvre and bargain for price reduction on the part of the buyer and strategies to sell his wares on the part of the sellers. It facilitates understanding between linguistically diverse interlocutors and supports social functions such as politeness, persuasion, and relationship-building. Code-switching serves pragmatic purposes such as clarification, persuasion, negotiation and politeness. These functions demonstrate how multilingual speakers in rural contexts skillfully manipulate language choices to achieve communicative goals.

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